

Greener Journal of Library, Information and Archival Sciences

Use of Reference Sources and Services by Students in Adeyemi College of Education Library, Ondo, Ondo State, Nigeria

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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

The study focuses on the use of reference sources and services by students in ACE Library, Ondo, Ondo State, Nigeria. Reference sources are materials in the reference section while reference services are rendered by reference librarian in meeting the information need of users in the library. The study surveyed 405 students comprising 183 and 222 Degree and NCE students respectively from the five schools in the College. Questionnaire was used to collect data. All the 405 questionnaires that were administered were returned and found valid for analysis. The findings of the study among others show that 246(60.7%) had good understanding of what reference materials are; 222 (54.8%) have good understanding of what reference service entails and 295(72.8%) make use of reference materials in the College Library. The major challenges confronting the students in the use of reference materials include very old materials 82 (20.2%) and time wastage when searching for materials 75 (18.5%). It could be concluded that students make use of reference materials and have understanding of reference sources and services probably because both the Degree and NCE students have compulsory courses in Library Instruction Programme and Introduction to Library Studies respectively. From findings of the study, it could be recommended that new reference materials should be acquired to cover all courses and reference librarian should organise orientation for the students on the use of reference materials in the library.

Keywords: Reference, Sources, Services, Students, Education, Ondo, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

The reference section is very important in every academic library. For any library to have free flow of information, the reference section must be very functional. The responsibility of every library is not just to select, acquire and organize information materials, but to go as far as disseminating such information to its users. The reference section is that area in the library where users get in contact with the library properly. Nwalo (2003) affirmed this by pointing out that the reference department is another major area of the library where contact is made with the public. He went further to say staff of the reference department are image makers of the library.

Reference sources are materials/books that are consulted in the library alone i.e. they cannot be borrowed from the library. In these words, this section contains materials that cannot be read from cover to cover. Aina (2004) opined that they are documents that contain miscellaneous information on any topic be it an event or individual. Examples of these materials include the following; dictionaries, encyclopedias, atlases, yearbooks, biographies, gazetteers, index, abstracts and bibliographies etc. Reference service is one of the major services in the library Onifade and Sowole (2011) quoting Wittaker (1977) affirmed this by stressing that the reference service is one of the most essential services a library provides for its users as it is a service that allows information to flow efficiently from information sources to the enquirer. Nwalo (2003) averred that services offered by this section includes answering reference queries, user education, compilation of reading lists, compilation of bibliographies, indexing and abstracting, inter library loan service and current awareness services.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Investigation has revealed that most students are not even aware of the various services rendered in the reference section. Ademodi (2004) and Onifade and Sowole (2011) both agreed in their various studies that one major conclusion that was drawn from their studies was that most of the respondents were not aware of reference services being offered in the library. It is in this regard this study tends to investigate the use of reference materials in the college library.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study are to:

- (1) Find out students perception of reference materials;
- (2) Determine students' perception of reference services;
- (3) Find out reference sources students mostly use; and
- (4) Ascertain the purpose of using reference sources in the library.

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered in this study:

- (1) What is the perception of students of Adeyemi College of Education, Ondo on reference materials?
- (2) What is the perception of Adeyemi College of Education, Ondo students on reference services?
- (3) Which of the reference materials are being mostly used by students of Adeyemi College of Education, Ondo?
- (4) What are the purposes why the students' of the College are using of reference materials?

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The outcome of the study is of great importance to the College Management and Reference Librarian(s) of Adeyemi College of Education, Ondo in improving reference sources and services respectively in the College Library and academic libraries in general to meet the information needs of users.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Reference sources/materials/books are not meant to be read from cover to cover but to be consulted for certain information or facts; these books are expected to be in the library at all times (Ruteyan and Akporhonor, 2007 citing Nwogu, 1991). The reference sources are kept in the reference section of the library for reference purpose and not to be borrowed. Librarians allow users to make photocopy of needed pages of the materials in the Reprography unit of the library. In an academic library, reference sources are to assist the lecturers and students in teaching and learning processes respectively. Reference sources consist of encyclopaedias, dictionaries, handbooks, yearbooks, directories, bibliographies, biographies, geographical sources etc. According to Elmer E. Ramuson and Biosciences Libraries (2009), reference sources such as dictionaries, encyclopedias, almanacs, atlases etc are research tools that can help in writing a paper and project. The materials provide answers to specific questioning such as brief facts, statistics and technical instructions; provide background information, or direct one to additional sources. There are direct reference sources like abstract, index and bibliographies and source reference material such as dictionaries, yearbooks, encyclopaedias, handbooks etc.

Reference service is the personal assistance rendered to library users by the Reference Librarian. According to Idris, Oji and Abana (2011) citing Gama (2008), reference service is the personal assistance given by librarians to users in pursuit of information; the assistance could be inform of information itself or it could be any library activity deliberately designed to facilitate easy retrieval of information. Reference services are one of the essential services provided in the library. It is one of the visible expressions of the library's purpose and mission. No wonder Ifidon (1997) sees reference services as the spring-board to the library and librarianship, wherein one is involved with all aspects of information both theoretical and practical. It is therefore, very important for Reference Librarian most especially in an academic library to make their services available to users and give them the opportunity to be aware of the services.

On the use of reference sources by undergraduates, Ademodi (2004); Onifade and Sowole (2011) discovered that encyclopaedias 53 (29%) and dictionaries 32 (18%); dictionaries 72 (21.1%) and encyclopaedias 66(19.3%) are mostly being used among the undergraduates in Adekunle Ajasin University, Akungba-Akoko and Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta respectively. Furthermore, Onifade and Sowole (2011) found out that majority of the respondents in their study do not know the difference between reference services and sources.

There are challenges confronting undergraduates in the effective use of reference sources. Onifade and Sowole (2011) discovered that reference materials available are very old and therefore not relevant to their study. Despite the fact that reference materials are old, it may not be totally truthful that they are not relevant to the undergraduates in an Agricultural based university. On the basis of above findings, it is necessary to investigate the use of reference sources by students of Adeyemi College of Education, Ondo.

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive survey design was adopted for this study. The population of the study constitutes the NCE and Degree students of Adeyemi College of Education, Ondo. Four hundred and five students were used as sample and they covered the five schools in the college. Questionnaire was used to collect data from the respondents. The College Library was used to administer questionnaire to the respondents.

Analysis

TABLE 1: POPULATION AND SEX OF RESPONDENTS

SEX	POPULATION	PERCENTAGE %
FEMALE	251	62%
MALE	154	38%
TOTAL	405	100%

Table 1 reveals that of the sample study of four hundred and five (405) respondents, 62% were females while 38% were males; showing a 100% response rate.

TABLE 2: DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BY SCHOOLS

SCHOOL	DEGREE	%	NCE	%	TOTAL	%
EDUCATION	87	21.5	15	3.7	102	25.2
SCIENCE	36	8.9	52	12.8	88	21.7
LANGUAGES	28	6.9	18	4.4	46	11.3
ARTS & SOC	59	14.5	39	9.6	98	24.1
VOC & TECH	44	10.9	27	6.7	71	17.6
TOTAL	254	62.7	151	37.2	405	100%

Table 2 shows that 102 (25.2%) of the respondents are from School of Education while 46 (11.3%) are from School of Languages.

Research question 1: What is the perception of students of Adeyemi College of Education, Ondo on reference materials?

TABLE 3: PERCEPTION OF STUDENTS ON REFERENCE MATERIALS

RESPONSE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
They are textbooks in the library	53	13%
They are books to be read from cover to cover and can be borrowed	39	9.6%
They are materials to be consulted for specific information and not to be read from cover to cover	246	60.7%
They are materials to be read from cover to cover but not to be borrowed	32	7.9%
No idea	35	8.6%

Table 3 reveals that 60.7% of the respondents have a good understanding of what reference materials are.

Research Question 2: What is the perception of Adeyemi College of Education, Ondo students on reference services?

TABLE 4: PERCEPTION OF STUDENTS' ON "REFERENCE SERVICE"

RESPONSE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
When one asks questions in the library	15	3.7%
When one receives assistance from the librarian	21	5.1%
When one consults reference materials	92	22.7%
When one is directed to certain information or sources of such information	222	54.8%
When a librarian helps a user	26	6.4%
No idea	29	7.1%

Table 4 shows that 222 (54.8%) of the respondents knew exactly what a reference service entails while 92 (22.7%) misunderstood the consultation of reference sources to be reference service.

TABLE 5: USE OF REFERENCE MATERIALS

RESPONSE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
YES	295	72.8%
NO	110	27.1%
TOTAL	405	100%

From Table 5, it was revealed that majority of the respondents 295 (72.8%) make use of reference sources.

Research question 3: Which of the reference materials are being mostly used by students of Adeyemi College of Education, Ondo?

TABLE 6: MOSTLY USED REFERENCE SOURCES

SOURCE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Handbooks	109	26.9%
Dictionaries	200	49.3%
Geographical Sources e.g. Maps, Atlases etc	62	15.3%
Indexes	56	13.8%
Abstracts	54	13.3%
Encyclopedias	239	59%
Directories	33	8.1%
Bibliographies	64	15.8%
Yearbooks	51	12.5%
Biographical sources e.g. Who's Who	45	11.1%
Manuals	61	15%

Table 6 shows that encyclopedias 239 (59%) and dictionaries 200 (49.3%) have higher rates of use than other reference sources in the library.

Research question 4: What are the purposes why the students' of the College are using of reference materials?

TABLE 7: PURPOSE OF USING REFERENCE MATERIALS

RESPONSE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
To write assignments	206	50.8%
To enrich lecture notes	140	34.5%
For pleasure/ leisure	64	15.8%
For personal knowledge	202	49.8%
For research	212	52.3%
To write projects	113	27.9%

Table 7 reveals that the respondents make use of the reference sources more for research 212 (52.3%) and assignment 206 (50.8%) purposes than any other reason.

TABLE 8: CHALLENGES TO USE OF REFERENCE MATERIALS

RESPONSE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
There are inadequate materials for my course	40	9.8%
Staff are not available to assist me	31	7.6%
I waste a lot of time when searching for materials	75	18.5%
The materials are very old	82	20.2%
I don't know how to make use of the materials	30	7.4%
I don't always get the information I need	60	14.8%
I don't ask the library staff to assist me in the reference section	33	8.1%
Tables and chairs are not enough for students in the reference section	23	5.6%
The reference section is not conducive for reading	53	13%

Table 8 reveals old reference sources 82 (20.2%) and wasting a lot of time when searching for reference sources 75 (18.5%) constitute the major challenges confronting the respondents in the use of reference sources in Adeyemi College of Education Library, Ondo.

TABLE 9: SUGGESTED SOLUTIONS FOR EFFECTIVE USE OF REFERENCE SOURCES AND SERVICES

SUGGESTIONS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
New reference materials should be acquired to cover all courses	300	74%
Staff should be ready to assist users	194	47.9%
There should be orientation on use of reference materials	229	56.5%
Students should be more serious during lectures on library Instruction Program	179	44.1%
Reference materials on CD-ROM should be provided for students use	122	30.1%
Air conditioners should be provided to make the section more conducive for reading	159	39.2%
More tables and chairs should provided	113	27.9%

Table 9 reveals that new reference materials should be acquired to cover all courses 300 (74%) and there should be orientation on the use of reference materials 229 (56.5%) as the major suggested solutions to improve the use of reference sources and services in the library.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The findings of the study show that 246(60.7%) have good understanding of what reference materials are; 222 (54.8%) have good understanding of what reference service entails and 295(72.8%) make use of reference materials in the College Library. Despite these, minority do not know that when one receives assistance from the reference librarian, it is a form of reference service.

Furthermore, it was found from the study that encyclopedias 239 (59%) and Dictionaries 200 (49.3%) have higher rates of use than other reference sources in the library. The finding is in tandem with the findings of Ademodi (2004), Onifade and Sowole (2011). Both Dictionaries and encyclopaedias are very relevant for undergraduates research and assignments. The purpose of the use of reference sources by the respondents are for research 212 (52.3%) and assignment 206 (50.8%) purposes.

The major challenges confronting the respondents' use of reference sources and services are that, the materials are old and wasting a lot of time when searching for reference sources. In a similar finding, Onifade and Sowole (2011) discovered that reference materials available in Federal University of Agriculture Library, Abeokuta are very old and therefore not relevant to their study.

CONCLUSION

From the findings of the study, it could be concluded that the reason for the positive result of the majority of respondents having full knowledge of reference sources and services, and making use of reference sources may be because of the effective teachings of library education to the students by librarians in the College Library.

RECOMMENDATIONS

For effective reference services in Adeyemi College of Education Library, Ondo in consonance with the findings from the study, we wish to recommend that:

- 1.The College Librarian in consultation with the Management should make efforts in acquiring new reference sources to cover all courses being offered in the College.
- 2.Reference Librarian(s) should make arrangement for orientation every session for the students on the use of reference sources and services in the library.
- 3.Library staff should endeavour to assist users in the reference section in their quest for information.
- 4.Both NCE and Degree students should be more serious during lectures on library education.

REFERENCES

- Ademodi, T.D. (2004). Students Awareness of Reference services in Adekunle Ajasin University Library, Akungba Akoko. *Owena Journal of Library and Information Science*, 1 (1)1-12.
- Aina, L.O. (2004). *Library and Information Science Text for Africa*. Ibadan: Third World Information Service.
- Elmer E. Rasmuson and Biosciences Libraries. (2009). Reference services and sources. Retrieved May 24, 2013 from file:///C:/User/Documents/Is 101-reference-services.htm
- Idris, H; Oji, E and Abana, E. F. (2011). Assessment of Reference provision of three libraries in Nigeria with particular reference to Ramat Library. University of Maiduguri, Ramat Polytechnic Library, Maiduguri, and Ibrahim Musa Library. *Information and Knowledge Management*, 1 (3), 2.
- Ifidon, S.E. (1997). *A guide to Reference Services*. Lagos: St. Micheal.
- Nwalo, K.I.N. (2003). *Fundamentals of Library Practice*. Ibadan: Stirling Horden Publishers.
- Onifade, F.N. and Sowole, A.O. (2011). Awareness and Perception of Reference Services by Undergraduate Students: A Case Study of the University of Agriculture, Abeokuta, Nigeria. *Gateway Library Journal*, 14 (1), 54-65.
- Ruteyan, J.O. and Akporhonor, B.A. (2007). An Assessment of the Reference collection and Services of four academic libraries in Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice*. Retrieved May 24, 2013 from file:///C:/User/Documents/Reference%20sources.%Delta.htm